

Open Science Strategic Blueprint

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1.1	2025-Aug.	The Software Heritage Open Science strategic blueprint for academia.	Morane Gruenpeter, Sabrina Granger, Roberto Di Cosmo, Jean-François Abramatic, Laetitia Cruse, and Nicole Martinelli Contact: morane@softwareheritage.org

Abstract: The **Open Science Strategic Blueprint** outlines a roadmap for applying Open Science practices to software. It defines shared goals, outlines concrete steps, and documents products, relationships, and activities to make software a recognized pillar of Open Science. The blueprint is grounded in the mission of Software Heritage: to collect, preserve, and share all publicly available source code as a common good for research and society. Its success depends on the people who contribute, adopt, and advocate for software as an essential part of the scholarly ecosystem..

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List of acronyms

ALIG	Archives and Libraries Interest Group
BSO	Baromètre français de la science ouverte / French Open Science Monitor
CNRS	Centre national de la recherche scientifique / French National Centre for Scientific Research
COSO	Comité pour la science ouverte / French Committee for Open Science
CRKN	Canadian Research Knowledge Network
CSAL	Consortium of Swiss Academic Libraries
DIG	Deposit Interest Group
ENS Lyon	Ecole Normale Supérieure de Lyon
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FOSS	Free and Open-Source Software
GRICAD	Grenoble Alpes Recherche - Infrastructure de Calcul intensif et de Données / High-Performance Computing and Data Infrastructure
INRAE	Institut national de recherche pour l'agriculture, l'alimentation et l'environnement / French National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food, and the Environment
INRIA	Institut national de recherche en sciences et technologies du numérique / National Institute for Research in Digital Science and Technology
MESR	Ministère de l'enseignement supérieur et de la recherche / French Ministry of Higher Education and Research
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
OSPO	Open Source Programme Office
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RSE	Research software engineers
SCAI	Source Code and AI Interest Group
SCOSS	Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services
SIRS (report)	Scholarly infrastructures for research software
SWH	Software Heritage
SWHID	SoftWare Hash Identifier

1 GOALS

1.1 Building an Open Infrastructure in the Open Science landscape

An **archive** and **catalog** of software source code is crucial for science to ensure preservation, accessibility, and findability of code artifacts. It guarantees the long-term availability and reproducibility of scientific outputs, supports software citation, and promotes software as a first-class research output in the scientific ecosystem. By preserving the software source code, it safeguards embedded scientific and technological knowledge. Building the software pillar of Open Science alongside and in connection with the Open Access repositories and Open Datasets repositories.

Figure 1: The Three Pillars of Open Science: Open Datasets repositories, Open Access repositories, and Open Source repositories

1.2 Making a culture change at different strategic levels

Since 2016, academia has increasingly recognized software as a scholarly contribution.

To address the research sector's needs, Software Heritage is building a mutualized infrastructure, catering to all domains and sectors that produce and use software source code. SWH is developing diverse services and tools, creating specific products for Open Science. Software Heritage is also investing in connecting communities, advocating for standards (the SWHID, CodeMeta, BibLaTeX @software). Connecting with institutions, policy organizations, and funding agencies helps ensure adoption at different levels. This approach, inspired by [Brian Nosek's \(2019\) strategy](#), aims to transform the academic landscape for software recognition and archival.

1.3 Adoption loop: transforming opportunities into adoption

Building momentum for Software Heritage as a central infrastructure and community by seizing opportunities and providing targeted support.

The adoption strategy focuses on the following steps:

1. Raising **awareness**
2. Encouraging **consideration**
3. Driving **adoption**
4. Ensuring **retention**
5. Fostering **advocacy**

Figure 2: The adoption loop

In Open Science, we leverage opportunities at institutional (e.g., INRIA), national (France), European, and international levels through strategic partnerships with entities like MESR/COSO, EOSC, UNESCO, SCOSS, and more. The Academic SWH community includes academic members and sponsors, sw-h-science collaborators & researchers, academic ambassadors, and a network of deposit and mirror partners.

2 STAKEHOLDERS

Many stakeholders are involved in supporting the Software Heritage mission with different types of adoption, support, and contribution, building a large and engaged community. The term "**adopter**" is used instead of "customer" to better define the relationship between Software Heritage and its stakeholders. An adopter can be:

- **Monetary contribution:** funders, sponsors & members
- **Non-monetary contribution:** ambassadors and other contributors
- **Partners:** infrastructures integrated with SWH - similar to Business-to-Business (B2B) relationship, which we will refer to in the document as Infrastructure to Infrastructure (I2INF).
- **Users:** users who adopted SWH in their activities, at the individual level and the institutional level. These relationships are similar to a Business-to-Customer (B2C) relationship. In the document, we will use the two types of relationships:
 - Infrastructure to User (I2U) for individual relationships with end-users
 - Infrastructure to Institution (I2INS) for institutional-level relationships, where an institution adopts the usage of the Software Heritage archive.

In this blueprint, we focus on the academic stakeholders.

2.1 Funders, sponsors, and members

For the sustainability of the infrastructure and all operations, it is necessary to diversify as much as possible the monetary support, as presented in the 2018 strategic plan. Software Heritage established three funding mechanisms for monetary contributions from all sectors: sponsorship, membership program, and project funding.

2.1.1 Sponsorship

The [sponsor program](#) allows for direct support to the non-profit organization's operations. Organizations, institutions, universities, and other entities that financially support the Software Heritage archive. The [Sponsors page](#) is regularly updated, and all sponsors have access to a dedicated mailing list.

2.1.2 Membership programs

We offer various membership programs that allow contributions to our infrastructure.

The Deposit Interest Group ([DIG](#)¹) is a membership program where organizations contribute financially and receive adapted support to deposit source code artifacts into the archives.

In 2024, Software Heritage created the Archives and Libraries Interest Group ([ALIG](#)²) to expand the membership revenue stream and increase global collaborations and partnerships with research libraries.

The ALIG membership has helped Software Heritage strengthen its global network by recruiting new institutional members and supporting the new challenge in academia: archiving software.

Finally, in 2025, the Source Code and AI ([SCAI](#)³) Interest Group was established to build a shared vision for an ethical AI model. This membership is more relevant to the Industry sector funders.

2.1.3 Academic project funding

Funders and research institutions/organizations can use SWH to keep track of software assets for technology transfer, impact metrics, and strategy.

1. The EU Commission, through the [EOSC project funding umbrella](#) (cf. CROSSMINER, EOSC-Pillar, FAIRsFAIR, FAIRCORE4EOSC, and FAIR-IMPACT)
2. [CHIST-ERA](#) & ANR project funding (cf. SoFAIR)
3. The Alfred P. Sloan Foundation, which offers grants to external contributors, has been a supporter of the OSPO-RADAR project since April 2025.

¹ https://annex.softwareheritage.org/public/brochures/SWH_DIG_membership_program.pdf

² <https://www.softwareheritage.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/ALIG-sept18th-final-version-1.pdf>

³ https://annex.softwareheritage.org/public/brochures/SWH_SCAI_membership_program.pdf

2.2 The SWH community advocating for Open Science: Ambassadors and contributors

The ambassador network⁴ brings together volunteers who help align community actions with the overall strategy. The program is structured around four sub-communities, with the academic one being the largest. A wide range of professional backgrounds are represented: Research Software Engineers(RSE), researchers, data analysts, librarians, and more.

- The ambassadors expand the reach of the archive in research communities by delivering training sessions and talks, creating learning materials, and documenting use cases.
- The ambassadors come from diverse backgrounds, holding positions in university departments, research organizations, or policy initiatives (such as the CoSO).
- SWH provides the ambassadors with funds and opportunities to showcase their skills (e.g., invited talks, calls for papers).
- Software Heritage supports its ambassadors by providing training opportunities and learning resources. By adopting a "train the trainer" approach, the program aims to scale up its reach.

Challenges for the program

- Maintaining a participation framework: the purpose is to develop a set of various ways to get engaged in the SWH ambassadors community.
- Knowledge management: capitalizing on the resources and materials created by the program in a structured way.
- Expanding or supporting linguistic coverage to promote broader adoption.
- Include all career stages: early career professionals may bring constructive insights
- Gender representativeness: reducing the gender gap

Beyond formal allies, a vast network of community members actively advocates for Software Heritage. A Customer Relationship Management (CRM) system will help identify individuals and organizations that have adopted Software Heritage products and actively support its mission. This will enable us to engage with a broader audience more effectively.

2.3 Partnerships in the scholarly ecosystem: Infrastructures for Open Science

2.3.1 Deposit partners in Academia

Deposit partners are organizations that collaborate with Software Heritage to facilitate the archiving and preservation of software source code. These partners integrate their platforms with Software Heritage's deposit services, enabling backstage submission of software artifacts and/or metadata for long-term preservation.

⁴ <https://www.softwareheritage.org/ambassadors/>

Figure 3: Architecture of interconnected scholarly infrastructures supporting archival, reference, description, and citation of (research) software source code (from the SIRS report)

Below are the current deposit integrations mapped with the effort required to launch and/or maintain the integration. The table includes the infrastructure name, type, and current relationship type, divided into the three types of relationship below:

- **Infrastructure to Infrastructure (I2INF)** - similarly to Business to Business⁵ relationship, giving access and creating integration to other infrastructures that cater to end-users (e.g, researchers)
- **Infrastructure to Institution (I2INS)** - a relationship between SWH infrastructure and an institution that uses SWH directly and not through another infrastructure, similar to Business-to-Customer⁶ relationship
- **Infrastructure to User (I2U)** for end-users (software engineers, researchers, curators, etc.) - a relationship with the end-users is necessary to ensure adoption of institutions and infrastructures

The integration's impact on the comment section:

Table 1: Partnerships integrating infrastructure and the SWH archive for Open Science (May 2025)

Infrastructure type	Integration	Main feature used	Comment
Scholarly Repository	HAL	Deposit service	Impact at the national (FR) level on institutions, such as Inria, INRAE, and the Université de Lille.
Scholarly Repository	InvenioRDM/ Zenodo	Deposit service	Impact on an international level and potential with InvenioRDM for new integrations
Scholarly Repository	DANS / DataverseNL	Save Code Now	Impact at a national (NL) level
Scholarly Repository	NII / JAIROCloud	Deposit service	Impact on an international level in Japan
Publisher	Episciences	SWHID iFrame	Impact in the publishing sector as a platform that supports various journals

⁵ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Business-to-business>

⁶ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Direct-to-consumer>

Infrastructure type	Integration	Main feature used	Comment
Publisher	eLife	Save Code Now	Impact on biomedical research communication
Publisher	IPOL	Deposit Service	Impact as a citation example
Publisher	Dagstuhl	Save Code Now	Impact on the publisher's sector as a platform that supports various journals
Aggregator	swMATH	Save Code Now	Impact on the mathematics discipline
Aggregator	OpenAIRE	Save Code Now	Impact at the EU level with EOSC
Aggregator	FR Research Software Catalog	HAL integration	Impact at the national level
Aggregator	CORE	COAR Notify	Impact on Open Access repositories connected with the CORE platform
Monitor	Baromètre Science Ouverte (BSO)	HAL integration	Impact at the national level
Reproducibility-focused	REPLICABILITY STAMP	Save Code Now	Impact on reproducibility challenges
Reproducibility-focused	GUIX	Save Code Now	Impact on reproducibility challenges

2.3.2 Mirror partners in Academia

Mirrors are essential for the sustainability and resilience of the universal source code archive. Their responsibilities are vital to keeping the archive safe and available. A mirror is a full copy of the Software Heritage universal source code archive, operated in agreement with, but independently from, the Software Heritage organization. We're building an international network of mirrors to prevent information loss and simplify access to humanity's software heritage

Table 2: Mirror deployment status, May 2025

Mirror deployment	Comment
ENEA ⁷	In production since 2023
GRNET	In production since 2025
Unidue	Signed in 2024
IMDEA	To be signed in 2025

⁷ <https://www.softwareheritage.org/2023/12/14/enea-mirror-opening/>

2.3.3 Funded projects

Beyond technical integrations, Software Heritage is deeply engaged in collaborative projects that strengthen its role as a core Open Science infrastructure. These projects bring financial support, technical expertise, and connections to diverse communities. Key examples include:

- **European EOSC projects:** [CROSSMINER](#), [EOSC-Pillar](#), [FAIRsFAIR](#), [FAIRCORE4EOSC](#), [FAIR-IMPACT](#). These have placed Software Heritage at the heart of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), developing connectors, standards (CodeMeta, SWHID), and policy recommendations.
- **CHIST-ERA and ANR projects:** such as [SoFAIR](#), supporting reproducibility and the implementation of FAIR workflows for research software.
- **A.P. Sloan Foundation:** providing strategic funding, most recently for the [OSPO-RADAR](#) project, which develops a software assets dashboard for Open Source Program Offices (OSPOs).

These project-based partnerships support the ongoing development of the infrastructure, contribute to its visibility and sustainability, and strengthen Software Heritage's role in the global Scholarly Ecosystem.

2.4 Users: Institutions, researchers, curators, and support staff

Users are at the heart of the Software Heritage mission. They are not direct funders, but their practices, needs, and advocacy help shape the way institutions and infrastructures adopt Software Heritage. Users include both **institutions** (which organize and manage research at scale) and **individuals** (researchers, PhD students, librarians, and curators) who interact with SWH in their daily work.

2.4.1 Institutions

Institutions, including universities, research organizations, laboratories, and libraries, act as collective users of the Software Heritage archive. Their involvement is often the gateway to larger-scale adoption and integration.

- **Role in Open Science:** Institutions support and enforce policies for archiving and citing research outputs. They provide the organizational framework to ensure software created within their organization is preserved and made visible.
- **How they use SWH:**
 - Long-term preservation of software outputs.
 - Integration of SWH with institutional repositories (e.g., HAL, DSpace, InvenioRDM, INRIA Gitlab⁸).
 - Producing metrics and reports on software activity for evaluation and compliance.
 - Supporting their researchers and staff with tools, training, and policies for software management.
- **Impact:** Institutional uptake ensures sustainability and scalability of software archival practices, reinforcing software as a first-class research output.

⁸ <https://gitlab.inria.fr/explore>

2.4.2 End users

End users are essential for encouraging institutions and funders to support SWH, nevertheless, they are not considered “customers” since they're not paying for the service.

Our training materials, documentation, and brochures are designed for end-users, giving them the resources they need to influence decision-makers and gain support for Software Heritage..

Open Science encompasses a diverse range of end-users and use cases, including but not limited to:

- **Researchers and PhD students**
 - Archive and reference software used and created in articles
 - Find useful software
 - Get credit for developed software
 - Verify/reproduce/improve results
- **Laboratories & institution support staff**
 - Track software contributions - monitor Research Software sustainability
 - Produce reports
 - Maintain web page
- **Curators & archivists**
 - Access code and analyze metadata submissions in their own institution

3 CHALLENGES

To establish software as a recognized pillar of Open Science, Software Heritage must overcome five categories of challenges: landscape, sustainability, technical, communication, and awareness. Each challenge reflects real problems observed today, alongside strategic responses and indicators for measuring progress.

#1 Landscape challenges (High)	
The external environment in which Software Heritage operates; the broader Open Science ecosystem of policies, infrastructures, and institutional practices.	
Problems today	Strategic response
Open Science adoption is uneven, and software is still undervalued as a research output.	Software Heritage builds alliances with international, regional, and community networks (e.g., EOSC, UNESCO, SCOSS) and advocates for policies that place software at the same level as data and publications.
Infrastructures remain fragmented and siloed.	Through membership groups (ALIG, DIG) and project involvement (FAIRCORE4EOSC, FAIR-IMPACT), SWH promotes convergence and interoperability across infrastructures.
Indicators <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The number of countries and institutions adopting software as a recognized research output. • The number of active collaborations in EOSC and international consortia. • The Inclusion of SWH in national and international Open Science policies. 	
Risks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slow recognition: If institutions don't recognize software as a research output, researchers won't deposit their code, and adoption will stagnate. • Fragmentation: If infrastructures remain siloed, integration with SWH will be costly, inconsistent, and harder to scale. • Lost momentum: If the international policy landscape doesn't converge, SWH risks being framed as a specialized tool rather than a core research infrastructure. 	

#2 Sustainability challenges (High) Ensuring Software Heritage has reliable funding, strong partnerships, and resilient infrastructure to scale and endure over the long term.	
Problems today	Strategic response
Today, Software Heritage benefits from a stable base of sponsors and members. The main challenge is to secure these contributions yearly and to expand the community of financial supporters with new contributors.	Develop diversified revenue streams through membership programs, sponsorships, and international partnerships, complemented by project-based funding. Promote the value of Software Heritage as essential infrastructure for research to ensure continued and growing investment.
The mirror network is still small (two active mirrors, two in progress), limiting resilience.	Grow the international mirror network by securing dedicated funding streams to support deployment and maintenance. Combine institutional partnerships (universities, national libraries, HPC centers) with co-funding models from sponsors and public funders.
Indicators <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Growth in the number and diversity of sponsors, members, and funding streams. ● Percentage of operating costs covered by recurring contributions (vs. project funding). ● Number of operational mirrors worldwide and their geographic distribution. 	
Risks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Renewal uncertainty: Annual renewal of contributions is not guaranteed, creating instability for long-term planning. ● Scaling gap: As adoption grows, costs for infrastructure (storage, mirrors, maintenance) may rise faster than revenue. ● Mirror slow deployment: Negotiations and technical onboarding can take years without dedicated funding and staffing. 	

#3 Product challenges (Medium) Building the right tools and standards, making sure the academic community actually uses them.	
Problems today	Strategic response
<p>Software-related products and standards face both technical and adoption barriers.</p> <p>Many institutional systems still lack interoperability with Software Heritage deposit workflows. In addition, metadata standards like CodeMeta and persistent identifiers like SWHID aren't yet widely adopted in academia.</p>	<p>Invest in product development that combines technical robustness with community adoption. Advance metadata workflows (CodeMeta, SWHID) and ensure they are embedded into institutional repositories through integration protocols (SWORD v2.0, COAR Notify).</p>
<p>Demand for advanced features (e.g. search, metadata visualization, citation support) outpaces current development capacity, limiting visibility and recognition of software as a research output.</p>	<p>Continue to deliver roadmap features such as bulk save, the software assets dashboard, and citation services to directly support academic use cases.</p>
<p>Awareness and practical use of Software Heritage products (CodeMeta, SWHID, citation tools, deposit workflows) remain limited across academia. Many researchers are unfamiliar with how to integrate these tools into their daily work, and institutions often lack concrete examples of successful implementation.</p>	<p>Increase visibility through ambassador-led training, publications, and reproducible research pilots, encouraging researchers and institutions to integrate these products into their daily workflows.</p>
<p>Indicators</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of repositories and infrastructures with active SWH deposit integrations. • Uptake of CodeMeta and SWHID in academic repositories, publications, and workflows. • Availability and adoption rates of key features (search, citation, dashboard). • Growth in ambassador-led training sessions and institutional pilots demonstrating product use. 	
<p>Risks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low adoption: Researchers and institutions may not adopt CodeMeta, SWHID, or citation tools if they are unaware of their existence or benefits. • Fragmented practices within the scholarly ecosystem: Without shared standards, software will continue to be referenced inconsistently, limiting interoperability. • Slow institutional uptake: Universities and research organizations may delay adopting policies and practices if there are no concrete pilots or demonstrated value. • Wasted development effort: New features (e.g., software assets dashboard, bulk save) risk underuse if the community is not ready to incorporate them into workflows. 	

#4 Communication challenges (Medium)	
Making sure the right message reaches the right audience in the right format, so that Software Heritage gains recognition and support across the academic ecosystem.	
Problems today	Strategic response
Messages need to be tailored to very different audiences: funders want sustainability metrics, researchers need citation and deposit guidance, while librarians seek workflows and training.	Develop tailored materials for each stakeholder group (funders, institutions, researchers, librarians, policymakers).
Many training and outreach materials remain scattered and are not always updated.	Expand the SWH Academy as a central hub for training and documentation, using a “train the trainer” model.
Limited staff capacity slows down the production of multilingual, discipline-specific, or career-stage-adapted materials.	Strengthen ambassador knowledge management through shared repositories, multilingual materials, and community coordination. Increase outreach capacity by aligning communication staff and community programs with Open Science goals.
Indicators <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number of updated and multilingual training materials available online. ● Number of ambassador-led training events or talks per year. ● Growth of community engagement metrics (newsletter reach, social media, event participation). ● Measured uptake of materials (downloads, views, citations). 	
Risks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Low visibility: Key stakeholders (funders, institutions, researchers) may remain unaware of Software Heritage’s role, reducing adoption. Key stakeholders (funders, institutions, researchers) may remain unaware of Software Heritage’s role, reducing adoption. ● Underused resources: Training and documentation may exist but remain invisible or inaccessible, limiting uptake by researchers and curators. ● Overreliance on individuals: Without structured knowledge management, communication depends too heavily on ambassadors or staff, creating fragility if contributors leave. 	

4 PRODUCTS, FEATURES, AND TOOLS

4.1 Products and features of SWH infrastructure

The following are existing and on the roadmap products and features to cater Infrastructure to Infrastructure (I2INF), Infrastructure to Institution (I2INS), and Infrastructure to end Users (I2U):

- **WebApp platform & API:** features relevant for Open Science include:
 - Save code now - I2INF, I2INS & I2U
 - Bulk save list (new in 2024) - I2INF, I2INS
 - Browse - I2U
 - Search (in the roadmap) - I2INF, I2INS & I2U
 - Reference with permalinks & SWHIDs - I2INF, I2INS & I2U
 - Citation (new in 2024) - I2U
- **Deposit service** - I2INF
 - SWORD protocol V2.0
 - APP capabilities - with timestamp (in the roadmap)
- **Software Assets dashboard:** to effectively archive, manage, and showcase software outputs. The dashboard will provide improved metadata management, simplified workflows, and increased institutional visibility, supporting a sustainable ecosystem for Research Software management. (in the roadmap and part of the OSPO-RADAR project)
- **Metadata workflow:** building the semantic web of FOSS for Open Science, linking articles, data, and software.
 - Intrinsic and [extrinsic metadata](#) indexing
 - Metadata export
 - Metadata visualization

3.2 SWHID specifications and standard

The [Software Hash IDentifier](#) is a big part of the Software Heritage archive and an external component that can be reused independently from the SWH infrastructure.

Specifications <https://www.swhid.org/> introduced by the SWHID Working Group

<https://groups.google.com/g/swhid-discuss> and in the ISO Standardisation process: The SWHID was officially published as the ISO/IEC international standard 18670 on April 23, 2025. [Official ISO Listing Free Public Specification](#)

3.3 BibLaTeX @software package

The [biblatex-software](#) package adds support for properly managing software entries in bibliographies for [BibLaTeX](#) users. Created by the SWH CEO, it is maintained by the SWH team.

CTAN package:

<https://www.ctan.org/tex-archive/macros/latex/contrib/biblatex-contrib/biblatex-software>

Specifications:

<https://gitlab.inria.fr/gt-sw-citation/bibtex-sw-entry/>

3.4 CodeMeta metadata standard, mappings, and tools

The community standard is used in the SWH indexer and is one of the assets in the Open Science strategy, developed in GitHub as a community-driven project, maintained by SWH team members. A [governance model](#) was put in place in 2023.

In 2024, [version 3.0](#) was released as part of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project goals, with a new open [w3id](#) identifier.

The CodeMeta maintainers are also responsible for:

1. The CodeMeta mappings are needed for the indexer and are currently not machine-actionable.
2. The CodeMeta generator is a community tool, contributed by SWH, useful in the researcher's workflow to make their software citable.
3. The CodeMeta website, including information and documentation on how to use CodeMeta

3.5 SWH Academy: Network, training, and tailored help-desk as a product

3.5.1 Members

Membership benefits for ALIG & DIG membership programs:

1. Access to a dedicated mailing list: group members are invited to the mailing list, which includes a quarterly newsletter.
2. Access to a training video on research software metadata curation, as well as live "train the trainer" sessions (starting in 2025, one or two per year).
3. Tailored help-desk support: A call with software archival specialists to identify the needs of the institution or organization in terms of support and to provide links to existing resources (HAL deposit guide, SWH archiving guide, Research Software Metadata guidelines, etc.).

If a consortium selects a Copper level or higher, the benefits apply to the entire consortium, not individual institutions. However, institutions contributing more than €8,000 can request individual consultations.

3.5.2 Partners

Partners eligible include organizations actively contributing to the Software Heritage mission through technical integration or infrastructure collaboration. This includes:

- **Deposit-partners:** Institutions with automated or semi-automated software deposit workflows into Software Heritage.
- **Mirror-network partners:** Organizations hosting a certified mirror of the Software Heritage archive to increase resilience and global accessibility.

3.5.3 Ambassadors

Ambassadors are local champions who promote Software Heritage within their institutions and communities. They receive early access to new features on the SWH archive platform, regular updates, and direct support from the team. Institutions with ambassadors are encouraged to join the ALIG or DIG programs for full benefits.

5 OUTREACH, COLLABORATIONS & SCALABILITY

5.1 Communication for Open Science

Open Science communication aims to raise awareness and drive engagement over several channels and formats. Current Open Science communication materials:

Learning resources

Guides, lessons, and posters that support and enhance learning and teaching open science

- [Archive and reference research software](#)
- Learning resources on software deposit in the scholarly repository HAL:
 - [End-users' guide](#)
 - [End-users' tutorial: a series of short videos](#)
 - Resources for the trainers: how to train for the software deposit
 - WIP in collaboration with the CCSD
 - Content is accessible to the persons who attended the session
 - [Moderators' guide](#) for information and metadata specialists
 - A [leaflet](#) for software deposit advocates
- [Implementation stories](#)
- Posters related to European projects:
 - [Posters](#) created for the FAIRCORE4EOSC project (2022-2025).
 - [Posters](#) created for the FAIR-IMPACT project (2022-2025).
- [Guidelines](#) for teams and individuals who provide support and tooling to researchers in various areas: PIDs, metadata, metrics, etc.
 - Quick access:
 - The FAIR-IMPACT [Guidelines for recommended metadata standards for research software within the EOSC](#)
 - [PIDs and research software description](#)
- (FR) "Préserver et rendre identifiables les logiciels de recherche avec Software Heritage": a guide for beginners, available on the Programming Historian website <https://programminghistorian.org/fr/lecons/preserver-logiciels-recherche>

Presentations

External communication about our work and resources used in open science teaching activities

- [Presentations](#)
- [Recorded presentations](#)
- [Presentations](#) related to the FAIRCORE4EOSC project (2022-2025). The FAIRCORE4EOSC project focuses on the development and realisation of core components for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).
- [Presentations](#) related to the FAIR-IMPACT project (2022-2025). The overall objective of FAIR-IMPACT is to support the implementation of FAIR-enabling practices across scientific communities and research outputs at a European, national, and institutional level.

Tutorials

Images and videos for learning and teaching purposes

- [GIFs and images](#)
- [The guided tour](#)
- [Videos](#)

Publications

<https://www.softwareheritage.org/publications/>

Technical documents

Technical roadmap, documentation, and technical reports related to open science projects

- [Current and past technical roadmaps](#)
- [Technical documentation for developers](#)
- [Technical documentation for sysadmins](#) (architecture)
- [Technical information: usage](#) (e.g. deposit service, listers and loaders)
- [Glossary](#)
- [The Software Heritage forge](#)
- [Technical reports](#) from the FAIRCORE4EOSC project (2022-2025).

Website pages

- <https://www.softwareheritage.org/save-and-reference-research-software/>
- <https://www.softwareheritage.org/how-to-archive-reference-code/>
- <https://www.softwareheritage.org/mission/science/>

5.2 Open Science collaborations in the Scholarly Ecosystem

Outreach activities are tailored to the relevant levels outlined below. These initiatives involve team members, community members, ambassadors, and other advocates who play a vital role in disseminating information and promoting the adoption of Software Heritage as an Open Science infrastructure.

Table 4: Open Science activities in Scholarly Ecosystem

Scope	Entity	Goal of activities
Institutional (INRIA)	IES & GT-Citation-Logiciel (INRIA)	Assist with software archival and metadata to support staff
Institutional (INRIA)	SED & BIL	Link internal INRIA tools with SWH & HAL
National	French Committee for Open Science MESRI / CoSO	Policy-level activities to reinforce software as a first-class output and software archival
National	French Committee for Open Science MESRI / CoSO	National Research Software Catalog project
National	ANR	Funding agencies' recommendations ANR 2023 guidelines (p. 17)
National	CCSD / HAL	Deposit, outreach & support collaboration. Creating materials and training for researchers, curators, and trainers.
National	Réseau français "Recherche reproductible"	Participation in representing software archiving as key for reproducibility
National	Guix	Collaboration for technical uptake of SWHIDs: reproducible research papers possible
National	National institutions	Collaboration and uptake in institutions: GRICAD / UGA, ENS Lyon, INRAE, CNRS, Couperin, and other potential FR ALIG members.
European	European institutions	Collaboration and uptake in institutions: CSAL /, and other potential EU ALIG members.
European	EOSC Ecosystem	Co-lead of EOSC TF / EOSC OA experts group: Research Software
European	SCOSS	Fundraising with 5th pledging round .
European	European funders	Effort and activities in Horizon Europe projects: FAIRCORE4EOSC / FAIR-IMPACT.

Scope	Entity	Goal of activities
European	European funders	Effort and activities in CHIST-ERA funded project: https://sofair.org/ .
Worldwide	SciCodes consortium	Participation in consortia, workshops, and activities.
Worldwide	CodeMeta	Maintenance and governance of CodeMeta initiative.
Worldwide	RDA (https://www.rd-alliance.org/)	Co-chair Software Source Code Interest Group and other working groups to reinforce software as a first-class output and software archival
Worldwide	FORCE11 (https://force11.org/)	Participate in FORCE11 activities
Worldwide	Zotero	Prospect for @software citation uptake
Worldwide	ORCID	Collaboration on the adoption of SWHID & using ORCIDs in SWH
Worldwide	Worldwide institutions	Collaboration and uptake in institutions: CRKN, NII (Japan), CAUL (Australia), and other potential ALIG members.
Worldwide	Worldwide initiatives	Adoption in initiatives: ARDC (Australia), COAR - the Coalition of Open Access Repositories

5.3 Scalability

Scaling Open Science operations involves planning and implementing processes to ensure that efforts can grow sustainably without over-committing.

1. Infrastructure and Technology:

- Analyze the impact of new infrastructure integrations on our current system and determine the additional requirements needed as the user base grows.
- Automate workflows, such as deposit & mirror partner onboarding.
- Ensure the API and WebApp platform can easily integrate new Open Science features, namely the search engine and software assets portal.

2. Human resources contributing to Open Science operations:

- Hire or onboard additional team members to the Open Science agenda, with training and onboarding programs for new hires and ambassadors to ensure integration.
- Utilize external resources, like contractors or consultants, for specialized or temporary tasks (e.g., documentation or technical writing).

3. Processes & systems for relations management:

- Define and standardize processes across teams to reduce manual and redundant actions that can be automated.

- Implement robust project management and CRM tools to manage collaborations, track progress, and monitor engagement.
 - Develop clear documentation and workflows to ensure processes are easily reproducible as the team grows.
4. Engage and grow the community:
- Scale outreach activities by leveraging ambassadors & community members to extend the reach of Open Science initiatives.
 - Develop educational resources, like webinars and online tutorials, to train a larger audience.
 - Foster partnerships and collaborations at different regional and international levels.
5. Secure sustainable funding:
- Diversify funding sources by engaging with new sponsors, partners, and grant opportunities.
 - Maintain strong relationships with existing funders.
6. Measure and Adapt:
- Continuously measure the performance of scaled operations using metrics such as user engagement, system uptime, and community growth.
 - Use data-driven insights to refine strategies, processes, and technologies as needs evolve.

These scalability strategies for Open Science operations ensure sustainable and natural growth of the team and efficient service delivery.

6 CALL TO ACTION

The foundations are here: a universal archive of source code, SWHIDs now standardized by ISO, and a growing community of sponsors, members, partners, and ambassadors. What's needed now is a collective effort to make the Software Heritage infrastructure a fundamental part of open science.

We are calling on funders, infrastructures, institutions, and researchers to join a unified effort. Your collective action is needed to sustain the archive, embed software preservation into policies, and make SWHIDs a standard in scholarly communication. Every contribution matters.

The next decade is decisive. If we move together now, we can ensure that research software is visible, citable, and preserved for generations. If we wait, knowledge will be lost. Help us build the Great Library of Source Code as a lasting legacy for science and society.